

Polarizability of Buckminsterfullerenes and some aromatic hydrocarbons

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The atomic bond and molecular polarizabilities of some fullerenes and aromatic hydrocarbons have been calculated using variational method and delta-function electronic wave functions. The geometries of C₆₀, C₇₀ and the two stable forms of C₈₄ have also been optimised.

Lippincott and Stutman¹ proposed the use of one dimensional delta-function potential model to calculate the bond and molecular polarizabilities of simple systems. The model has been successfully applied to larger molecules²⁻⁴. In this communication we have applied the method for the determination of bond and molecular polarizabilities of fullerenes and some model aromatic hydrocarbons and compared the results with those obtained by Semwal and Balodi⁵, using Miller's⁶ method and available experimental values.

In recent years, Buckminsterfullerene and the rapidly growing family of related molecules have attracted much attention. A number of theoretical calculations have been performed on fullerenes in view of their novel geometries. The high symmetry of C₆₀ (I_h) enabled *ab initio* calculations with full geometry optimization^{7,8}. Even for fullerenes with lower symmetry such as C₇₀ and C₈₄, *ab initio* calculations have been carried out with full geometry optimization⁹. In this paper we report studies on the structure and polarizability of C₆₀, C₇₀ and C₈₄. While the structure, of C₆₀ and C₇₀ have been clearly established by earlier studies, the nature of C₈₄ has not been investigated in detail. The MNDO semi-empirical technique¹⁰ had identified two stable isomers of C₈₄. The first is a D_{6h} geometrical arrangement and the second is a T_d arrangement. In addition, a novel structure containing seven membered rings had also been considered for C₈₄. However, it is found to be significantly less stable than the structures, containing only five and six-membered rings. If we consider the chemical nature of these molecules, we find all the potential bonding modes of this carbon cluster. The true chemical nature of C₆₀ is however still unknown. Determination of bond lengths and related properties like polarizability, hyper-polarizability, dipole moment and magnetic susceptibility can further help in understanding the structural variations.

Polarizability calculations :

The average molecular polarizability (α_M) can be expressed in terms of its principal component α_{xx} , α_{yy} and α_{zz} as,

$$\alpha_M = 1/3 [\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy} + \alpha_{zz}] \quad (1)$$

where the principal components of the polarizability tensor are obtainable from the relation $P = \alpha E$. The molecular polarizability tensor α_j is obtained by combining principal components of it for total j -bonds in molecule, or

$$|\alpha_M^j| = \begin{vmatrix} \alpha_{xx}^j & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_{yy}^j & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_{zz}^j \end{vmatrix} \quad (2)$$

If bonds of molecule have rotational symmetry about their axes, the following assumption is possible¹¹.

$$\alpha_{yy}^j = \alpha_{xx}^j = \alpha_{\perp}^j \quad (3)$$

Thus the computation of average molecular polarizability is left with the evaluation of parallel and perpendicular components and hence to sum it over all the bonds to obtain aggregated α_M values. The concept of parallel and perpendicular components of polarizabilities and even the contribution by the non-bonding electrons to the parallel components is well documented in the delta-function potential technique¹.

The general expression for molecular polarizability expressed in Cartesian coordinate system is given by,

$$\alpha = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\sum_{i \neq 0} (\mu_x)_i^2 + (\mu_y)_i^2 + (\mu_z)_i^2}{E_i - E_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } (\mu_x)_i = (e \psi_i^* | \sum_j e x_j | \psi_0) \quad (5)$$

e is the electronic charge, ψ_0 is the ground-state delta-func-

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tion wave function, and E denotes the energy.

To calculate the molecular polarizabilities for the general class of polyatomic molecules, Lippincott and Stutman¹ proposed an alternative and simple method than solving through eq. (5) by the semi-empirical delta-function model of chemical bonding^{12,13}. Here delta-function model is obtained by replacing the coulomb potentials in Schrödinger equation of a molecular system with delta-function potentials. The molecular wave functions are obtained from the linear combinations of atomic delta-functions. On the basis of the variational treatment¹⁴ first introduced by Hylleraas¹⁵ and Hasse¹⁶, the xx component of the polarizability is expressed in the form :

$$\alpha_{xx} = \frac{4nA}{a_0} [(x_1 - \langle x \rangle)^2 - (n-1) \langle (x_1 - \langle x \rangle) (x_2 - \langle x \rangle) \rangle]^2 \quad (6)$$

where x is the coordinate of any one of n equivalence class of electrons, which falls in the first equivalence class, $\langle x \rangle$ is the average coordinate of any one of these electrons, A is the delta-function strength determined from the reduced electronegativity of the atom¹⁷ and a_0 is the radius of the first Bohr orbit. Since delta-function wave function does not allow interaction between the coordinates, $(x_1 - \langle x \rangle) (x_2 - \langle x \rangle) = 0$. The model with the mean delta-function strength predicts $x = 0$, so equation (6) becomes,

$$\alpha_{xx} = \frac{4nA}{a_0} [X_1^2]^2 \quad (7)$$

Molecular polarizability consists of parallel and perpendicular components of the constituents of the bond polarizabilities. The bond parallel component is obtained from the contributions by the bonding and non-bonding electrons of the valence shell. The contribution of the bonding electrons is calculated using a linear combination of atomic delta-function wave functions of the nuclei involved in the bond i.e. the expectation value of the electronic position squared $\langle X^2 \rangle^2$ along the bond axis is calculated, and this is used to evaluate the parallel component of bond polarizability $\alpha_{\parallel b}$ from the equation,

$$\alpha_{\parallel b} = \frac{4nA_{12}}{a_0} [\langle x^2 \rangle^2] \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where, } \langle x^2 \rangle = \frac{R^2}{4} + \frac{1}{2C_{R12}^2} \text{ and } A_{12} = (A_1 A_2)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

n is the bond order and R the internuclear distance at equilibrium configuration, and

$$C_{R12} = (n_1 n_2 N_1 N_2)^{1/4} (A_{12})^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where n_1, n_2 and N_1, N_2 stand for the principal quantum number and number of electrons making contribution to the bonding respectively. For a heteronuclear bond, a polarity correction must be made in the parallel component of the bonding electrons to account for the charge density introduced by the electronegativity difference of the atoms.

The degree of polarity ρ defined by Pauling¹⁸ is given as :

$$\rho = 1 - \exp^{-1/4} (x_1 - x_2)^2 \quad (11)$$

The charge density in the bond region then should be related to the percent covalent character,

$$\sigma = e^{-1/4} (x_1 - x_2)^2 \quad (12)$$

where X_1 and X_2 are the electronegativities of the atoms 1 and 2 respectively, on the Pauling scale¹⁸. The corrected value of parallel component of bond polarizability is given by,

$$\alpha_{11p} = \sigma \alpha_{11b} \quad (13)$$

The contribution of non-bonding electrons is calculated by evaluating the contribution of electrons in the valence shell of each atom not involved in the bonding. Such calculations are made on the basis of octet rule as modified by Linnett¹⁹ in terms of a double quartet of electrons. This can be expressed as,

$$\alpha_{11n} = \sum_j f_j \alpha_j \quad (14)$$

where f_j is the fraction of valence electrons in the j -th atom not involved in the bonding and α_j is the atomic polarizability of j -th atom. The perpendicular component of the bond polarizability was obtained by empirical approach of Lippincott and Stutman¹, which is expressed as,

$$\sum \alpha_{\perp j} = \frac{(3N - 2n_b)}{N} \sum_j \alpha_j \quad (15)$$

where N is the number of atoms and n_b is the number of bonds in the molecule. Taking into account the polarity correction the sum of the perpendicular components of the bond polarizability is given as,

$$\sum \alpha_{\perp j} = (3N - 2n_b) \sum_j \frac{X_j^2 - \alpha_j}{X_j^2} \quad (16)$$

or

$$\sum \alpha_{\perp j} = N df \sum_j \frac{X_j^2 - \alpha_j}{X_j^2} \quad (17)$$

where $ndf = (3N - 2n_b)$. The residual atomic polarizability

degree of freedom obtainable from the consideration of symmetry and geometry of the molecular type.

Now the average molecular polarizability with no bond polarity corrections can be written as,

$$\alpha_M = \frac{1}{3} \left[\sum_j \alpha_{11b} + \sum_j f_j \alpha_j + \frac{3N - 2n_b}{N} \sum_j \alpha_j \right] \quad (18)$$

and with bond polarity correction it will be,

$$\alpha_M = \frac{1}{3} \left[\sum_j \alpha_{11p} + \sum_j f_j \alpha_j + n_{df} \sum_j \alpha_j \frac{X_{ij}^2 \alpha_j}{X^2 j} \right] \quad (19)$$

Eq. (19) is used in the present calculation of average molecular polarizabilities.

Structure of fullerenes :

C₆₀ : Buckminster fullerene (C₆₀) was initially observed as a mass peak in a carbon cluster beam²⁰⁻²² which corresponds to a cation derived from a C₆₀ structure of a truncated Icosahedron (*I_h* symmetry), Fig. 1, C₆₀ has already been studied theoretically²³⁻³⁸ and we report our results on this molecule only as a calibration of the techniques used. The soccer ball structure of C₆₀ has 20 hexagons and 12 pentagons. Luthi and Almlöf²⁹ reported the bond length in five membered rings as 1.453 Å and that between two six membered rings as 1.369 Å .

Fig. 1. Icosahedral C₆₀ structure viewed down a 5-fold axis.

C₇₀ : C₇₀ has a *D_{5h}* geometry where a cylindrical belt of 10 atoms has been added to C₆₀ to yield a prolate spheroidal structure like rugby ball. Fig. 2 shows the geometry of C₇₀ including the ellipsoidal distortion. Fig. 3 shows a somewhat different perspective illustrating how the atoms are arranged in different planes. It also shows that there are five distinct types of carbons. Geometrically, the most interesting aspect of C₇₀ corresponds to the nature of the bonding and strain around the 10 added carbon atoms. These atoms are all at the junction of these hexagons and thus most resemble the carbon in the graphite. In fact the chemical shift corresponding to these carbons is well separated from that of the other carbons which are all part of five-membered

rings. The different bond lengths and bond angles are given in Table 2. One method for considering the strains and hybridization originally proposed by Haddon and Scott³⁹. In this scheme, the σ bonds are assumed to lie along the internuclear axes and the orbital. Orthogonality relationships are used to solve for the π -orbitals hybridization and direction.

Fig. 2. *D_{5h}* form of C₇₀, viewed perpendicular to the 5-fold axis and showing the prolate spheroidal structure.

Fig. 3. Numbering system for C₇₀, showing planar arrangement of its atoms.

In particular the σ - π inter orbital angle is good measure of the local curvature of the spheroid and has a value 101.6° for C₆₀, for C₇₀ 96.2° for the cylindrical belt of atoms. For the completely optimized structures in this work, the σ - π angle at the different carbon centres varies from 98.8 to 102.0°. This small range of values indicates more uniform curvature around the spheroid than is the case for the idealized structure.

C₈₄ : The structures of C₆₀ and C₇₀ as considered above, are unique and are now well established. However, for C₈₄, there are many structural possibilities that give rise to a large number of local minima. The highly symmetric structures of C₆₀ and C₇₀ suggest that stable spheroidal arrangements of atoms can be obtained by distributing the strain in the system as uniform as possible. If we assume that the structure consists of only five and six membered rings, the local strain is due to the presence of the pentagonal rings,

since it is well known that 12 five membered rings lead to closure, such a structures of C_{84} would also contain 32 six membered rings. We have attempted to derive structures that have the five membered rings distributed uniformly.

In addition we require that no two pentagon share an edge, since the strain in such cases would preclude any stable arrangement. With these constraints in mind, we have examined two different structures for C_{84} that are highly symmetric and stable. The first is a D_{6h} geometrical arrangement (Figs. 4 and 5), originally proposed by Fowler³⁶. This structure can be thought of as being analogous to C_{70} in that it can be obtained by replacing the C_{70} 5-fold symmetry axis by a 6-fold axis. The 12 five membered rings are separated from each other and are, in fact, equivalent by symmetry. As for C_{70} the geometry is spheroidal. However, where C_{70} is a prolate spheroid, C_{84} is an oblate spheroid, similar to C_{70} , there are five kinds of atoms and thus five peaks are expected in a ^{13}C NMR spectrum. The D_{6h} structure has 12 structural degrees of freedom. An interesting aspect of the D_{6h} structure is that, unlike C_{60} and C_{70} , two of the hexagons in this structure are surrounded completely by other two hexagons. The curvature around these carbons is of interest in determining whether the local environment is close to planarity, as in graphite. However, inspection of the σ - π interorbital angle (Table 2) yields a value of 97.0° , considerably different from the ideal graphite value of 90° . In fact, detailed examinaion of the curvature around all carbons. Table 2 shows that the strain is spread relatively uniformly around all the atoms including those that do not

participate in the formation of five membered rings (The σ - π angle varies from 97.0 to 101.0°). It is also interesting to note that, unlike the case of C_{60} , no hexagon in this structure has more than two pentagons adjacent to it.

The second C_{84} structure is a T_d arrangement, originally suggested by Whetten *et al.*⁴⁰. This structure is shown in Fig 6, viewed down one of the 3-fold axes. Each corner of tetrahedron had 21 atoms as shown in Fig. 7. Again, all 12 five membered rings are equivalent. This structure has only four different kinds of atoms and thus would have only four peaks in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum. It contains four hexagons that are completely surrounded by hexagons. However, unlike the D_{6h} form, it also has four hexagons that have three pentagons adjacent to them, as in C_{60} . The σ - π angle varies from 97.0° to 101.9° , whowing a slightly less uniform curvature than the D_{6h} form, T_d form has only 11 degrees of freedom.

The above structures contain only five and six membered rings. Other structures are possible, if we also allow seven membered rings to be present. Simple geometrical argument show that each seven membered ring also introduces an additional five membered ring to cause closure. A highly symmetric C_{84} can be obtained by replacing the five fold axis of C_{60} with a seven fold axis. This structure shown in Figs. 8 and 9, has two seven membered rings, 14 five membered rings and 28 six membered rings. Due to the presence of 16 non-six membered rings. Such an arrange-

Fig. 4. D_{6h} form of C_{84} , viewed perpendicular to the 6-fold axis showing the oblate spheroidal structure.

Fig. 5. Numbering system for D_{6h} form of C_{84} , only the atoms in the front half are shown for clarity.

Fig. 6. T_d form of C_{84} , viewed down a 3-fold axis.

Fig. 7. Numbering system for T_d form of C_{84} , only the 21 atoms in one corner of the tetrahedron are shown for clarity.

ment is not expected to be in the ground state, and this is confirmed by the MNDO results. The D_{7d} form only has 10 degrees of freedom. These three structures of C_{84} are highly symmetric with only 12, 11 and 10 degrees of freedom completely determining their geometry. All these structures have been completely optimized at MNDO level. However, the high symmetry of the D_{6h} and T_d forms and the uniform nature of the strain of these spheroids indicate that these are likely to be among the most stable isomers. Both these C_{84} isomers are significantly more stable than either C_{60} and C_{70} . However, Whetten⁴⁰ shows that the NMR spectra are much more complicated containing many more lines. It is not clear if this is due to the presence of a more asymmet-

Fig. 8. D_{7d} form of C_{84} , viewed perpendicular to the 7-fold axis.

Fig. 7. Numbering system used for D_{7d} form of C_{84} , only the atoms in the front half are shown for clarity.

ric structure or due to the presence of several structural isomers. Higher levels of theory on these and other structural isomers may be necessary to identify the ground state geometry of C_{84} .

Results and discussion

The values of δ function potential average molecular polarizabilities (α_m) of C_{60} , C_{70} , C_{84} and model aromatic compounds are given in Table 1 along with available experimental values and the values calculated by using Miller's method.

Assuming the isotropic nature of atoms, the atomic polarizabilities along the X-axis (α_{xx}) were fixed using the delta-function strengths and relation ($\alpha_{xx} = 4/a_0^3 \text{ \AA}^3$). The delta-function atomic polarizabilities of hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen and oxygen are 5.92×10^{-25} , 9.78×10^{-25} , $7.43 \times$

Table 1. Polarizabilities (α_M) of some condensed aromatic hydrocarbons (10^{-25} cm^3)

Molecule	α_M	α_M	α_M
	Present work	Miller's method	(Expt.)
Benzene	111.552	104.50	103.9
Naphthalene	168.897	166.60	174.8
Anthracene	259.823	228.80	259.3
Naphthacene	300.311	291.06	322.7
Pentacene	339.485	353.25	436.8
Hexacene	404.255	415.44	—
Pyrene	271.03	256.23	293.4
Coronene	321.528	373.14	425.0
Acenaphthylene	154.102	194.04	206.1
Corannulene	268.551	310.95	—
Pyracylene	215.034	221.40	—
C_{60}	710.45	821.30	—
C_{70}	947.26	958.20	—
C_{84}	1278.81	1149.90	—

Table 2. σ - π Interorbital angle for C_{60} , C_{70} and C_{84}

Structure	Atom type	Angle
$C_{60} (I_h)$		101.6
$C_{70} (D_{5h})$	C_1	102.0
	C_2	101.9
	C_3	101.5
	C_4	100.0
	C_5	98.9
$C_{84} (D_{6h})$	C_1	97.0
	C_2	100.4
	C_3	101.0
	C_4	100.25
	C_5	98.9
$C_{84} (T_d)$	C_1	101.7
	C_2	100.9
	C_3	100.8
	C_4	96.8

10^{-25} and $5.92 \times 10^{-25} \text{ cm}^3$ respectively. The A-values are 1.000, 0.846, 0.927 and 1.000 in a.u. respectively. The polarizability is quite sensitive to geometry and therefore it would be better if the geometries be optimized at a common level of theory to avoid geometry effects in predictions. The small difference between calculated and experimental values may be attributed to the intermolecular interactions and may be related to the loosening effect caused by the slight displacement of protons, in the formation of hydrogen bonds between monomers. The more difference in certain cases like pyrene may be due to Van der Waals

interactions which caused tightening of electronic system of the molecules.

The deviation with experimental values may be caused due to several reasons of the mechanism of its structural interpretations i.e. the complex mechanism of distribution of bonds. Whereas for simplicity we have taken same bond order and same bond length for every environment without incorporating inductive effect. We observe α_{\parallel} and α_{\perp} do not vary greatly because most of the anisotropy is associated with the parallel and perpendicular directions (This contribution does not vary very much). While the anisotropy connected with Z and Y directions varies noticeably, but its contribution is much smaller. Also σ and π -electrons do not contribute equally to the bond parallel components of the polarizability and that the contribution of the electrons in the π -orbital is less than those in electrons in the σ -orbital. It is also found that the bond polarizabilities are not necessarily transferrable from one molecular system to another owing to the strong dependence of the bond parallel component on the bond length.

Further, it is now evident that fullerene-derived solids are equally exciting, from both the fundamental and technological view points and that these solids possess many novel properties of interest to physicists and material scientists. However, only a few derivatives of C_{60} have been reported, for example, the complex of C_{60} with metals^{42,43} such as the $C_{60}O_5O_4$, the C_{60} -platinum complex and a variety of doped system including boron³⁷, alkali^{45,46} and transition metals⁴⁷. Derivatives of the fullerenes will be an important area of research in terms of potential applications and the discovery of new properties. Hydrogenation of C_{60} via Birch reduction has been shown to yield, $C_{60}H_{36}$ ⁴⁸. Fluorination C_{60} and C_{70} has been reported⁴⁹, and the formation of $C_{60}F_{36}$, $C_{70}H_{40}$ and other-fluorinated $C_{60}S$ and $C_{70}S$ was confirmed from mass spectrometry^{49a}.

An oxide of C_{70} , $C_{70}O$ has also been generated and its existence was confirmed by mass spectrometry and infrared absorption spectra⁵⁰. Recently other species have been shown to add to the C_{60} cage^{51,52} including other halogens^{51a-c} and benzyl and alkyl radicals^{51d}.

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